

Analysis of the Neutronic Effect of the Axial Twist of Helical Cruciform Fuel Rods Using Peacock

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ABSTRACT

One of the possibilities in advanced nuclear fuel is the four-lobed helical cruciform fuel rod currently being developed by Lightbridge Corporation for existing light water reactors (LWRs). A particularity presented by this fuel is that it is difficult to model exactly using existing lattice physics codes. The twist along the length of the rod makes it impossible to model exactly in two dimensions, so for this work 3D Monte Carlo methods were used. Models of the rods were created using Peacock—the general geometry Monte Carlo code developed by Studsvik Scandpower. Even the geometry of traditional Monte Carlo methods, however is unable to perfectly model the twist of this fuel. To overcome this limitation, a method was developed for creating an approximate model of a helical cruciform fuel rod which uses discrete steps along the length of the rod. The accuracy of the method was tested, and guidelines were set for future use of the method. Models were created (within the determined guidelines) with various amounts of twist, and these models were used to show that twist does not have a significant effect on the reactivity of the rods.

Keywords: Helical Cruciform Fuel, Peacock, Monte Carlo, Lightbridge, Advanced Fuel

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, Monte Carlo methods have become increasingly common for neutronic modeling. One advantage of Monte Carlo is that its general geometry can more easily model advanced reactors and fuel. In this work, Monte Carlo methods are used to study the geometric effects of the four-lobed helical cruciform fuel rod similar to the one that is currently being developed by Lightbridge Corporation [1]. This fuel has a unique composition and geometry from other LWR fuel rods. Instead of being a cylinder, it is shaped similar to a plus sign, with rounded lobes that twist helically along the length of the rod. This work quantifies the reactivity effect of the axial twist.

The models for this work were created using Peacock—a general geometry Monte Carlo neutronics code developed by Studsvik Scandpower (SSP) [2] that uses constructive solid geometry (CSG) with second-order surfaces. In this work, the multiplication factor was the only result studied. All calculations in this work used cross section libraries developed internally at SSP based on the ENDF/B-VII.1 library.

Despite the capabilities of CSG, this fuel shape is still too complex to model using only the second-order surfaces available in Peacock and other traditional Monte Carlo codes. In order to be able to study the effects of twist, a discretization method was created to approximate the geometry of these rods. The method was to discretize the twist by separating the rod into a number of axial layers, and to have each layer be offset from the previous by a small amount of twist. An exact model of similar fuel has been demonstrated in other work using Bézier curves for Monte Carlo codes using a delta tracking method [3]. However, Peacock is currently based on the surface tracking method so this would require additional analytical work.

Ultimately, the goal of this work was to determine how reactivity changes with twist, but before that could be accomplished tests needed to be done to determine the accuracy of the discretization method.

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(a) General dimensions.

(b) Peacock cruciform pincell geometry colored by cell.

Figure 1. Cruciform fuel rod geometry.

These tests looked at how reactivity changed when the twist per discrete layer (*twist/layer*) was varied. Following this, the tests to determine the effect of the twist on reactivity with twist looked at the change in reactivity when the twist per axial height (*twist/cm*) was varied.

2. MODEL SPECIFICATIONS

2.1. Defining a Helical Cruciform Rod

Helical cruciform fuel rods are designed to operate in existing LWRs [1], so they are similar to existing LWR fuel in length and pitch, however there are major differences. Instead of a cylindrical shape, these rods have a four-lobed cross-sectional area that twists axially along the length of the rod. The fuel design offers advantages in heat transfer, self-spacing, and in other areas [1], however this work focuses solely on modeling the design and analyzing the effect of twist on reactivity. The two-dimensional cross section of a helical cruciform fuel rod is shown as the shaded region of Figure 1a. Figure 1b shows a two-dimensional cross section of a helical cruciform pincell created in Peacock with each color corresponding to a different cell.

Specifications for the material and geometry of the fuel rods were taken from publicly available sources (see Table I). A few additional simplifying assumptions were made in this work. The diamond central displacer was omitted and the models did not include burnable poisons. The thickness of the cladding in the Peacock models was modeled as uniform (omitting extra clad on the ends of the lobes [4]). The properties of the water were assumed to be the same as a typical PWR. When these models were created, Peacock did not support periodic boundary conditions, so in this work all calculations were performed with a mirror boundary condition in the radial direction. To highlight the difference, a cross section (at one point along the rod) of a small array of rods is shown in Figure 2a with mirror boundary conditions, and in Figure 2b with periodic boundary conditions.

The purpose of this work is to understand generally how the twist of a rod affects reactivity. Despite these simplifications, the results of this work give a general understanding of how twist affects reactivity.

Table I shows a summary of the specifications of the helical cruciform fuel rods modeled in this work. The magnitude of twist is varied. For reference, proposed amounts of twist include 1350° [1] and 658° [5] over the 365.76 cm length of the rod. These values correspond to about $3.9^\circ/\text{cm}$ and $1.8^\circ/\text{cm}$, respectively.

Figure 2. Helical cruciform fuel with differing boundary conditions.

Table I. Specifications of rods modeled in this work.

Measurement	Type	Value	Units	Reference
a (not including clad)	length	0.575	cm	[4]
b (not including clad)	length	1.06	cm	[4]
Clad Thickness	length	0.05	cm	[4]
Rod Length	length	365.76	cm	
Pitch	length	1.26	cm	[1]
Fuel Density	density	9.64	g/cm ³	[6]
Fuel Zr Fraction	wt%	50.0		[1]
Fuel U Fraction	wt%	50.0		[1]
Fuel U Enrichment	wt% U235	19.7		[7]
Clad Density	density	6.50	g/cm ³	[8]
Clad Zr fraction	wt%	99.0		[9]
Clad Nb fraction	wt%	1.0		[9]
Water Density	density	0.60	g/cm ³	
Water Boron Concentration	concentration	900	ppm	
Model Temperature	temperature	600	K	
Radial Boundary Condition	boundary condition	mirror		
Axial Boundary Condition	boundary condition	vacuum		

Figure 3. A Peacock-generated helical cruciform fuel rod that twists 0.72° /layer.

2.2. Axial Twist Discretization Method

As mentioned, the helical cruciform fuel rods cannot be modeled with CSG exactly using second-order surfaces, so a method was developed to discretize the twist. In this method, the rod is divided lengthwise into a number of equally-spaced layers. Each layer is offset from the layer before by a small amount of twist. This way, the twist is applied at discrete steps along the length of the rod. A rod could be approximated with any number of layers; the more layers that it has, the smoother the twist appears. Figure 3 shows a 20 cm long helical cruciform rod with 500 layers and a total axial twist of 360° —which results in 0.72° /layer.

Approximating the twist inevitably introduces some error into the model. It is reasonable to assume that when a high number of layers are used, the model is more accurate. The goal when creating a model is to minimize both error and the amount of cells and surfaces. This work sought to provide a guideline for the minimum amount of layers when using the discretization method.

3. DETERMINING THE ACCURACY OF THE DISCRETIZATION METHOD

3.1. Methods for Determining the Accuracy of the Discretization Method

The metric used to quantify the discretization method is twist/layer. This quantity determines how much each layer is offset from the layer before, and how much of an overhang there is at the nodes between layers. If the amount of twist of a rod is increased, then the amount of layers must also increase in order to maintain the same amount of twist/layer. As the amount of layers approaches infinity, the amount of twist/layer will approach zero. As the amount of twist/layer approaches zero, it is assumed that the error due to approximation also approaches zero.

Peacock uses surface tracking methods [2] which cause the runtime to increase significantly with an increasing amount of surfaces and cells. While less twist/layer causes the model to be more accurate, it also increases the runtime. A threshold value was sought for the maximum amount of twist/layer that provides acceptably accurate results.

One model twisted 0.984° /cm and the other twisted 9.984° /cm (360° and 3600° of total twist along the length of the rod respectively). Cases of each of the two models ranged from 0° /layer to 45° /layer. Each of these cases were run with either two-million or four-million particles per cycle, 50 inactive cycles, and 100 active cycles. 256 total cases were run, with standard deviations ranging from 3.7 pcm to 7.2 pcm.

To determine if a threshold value for twist/layer existed, all the data points were taken, and a least squares linear regression was performed. After this, the data point containing the largest twist/layer was removed, and the linear regression was performed again using the remaining points. This process was repeated until there was only a single data point left. In this work, if the slope plus or minus one standard deviation included both positive and negative values, then the slope was interpreted as indistinguishable from zero.

Table II. Selection of 9.984°/cm model linear regression results.

Threshold Value (°/layer)	Slope	σ	Slope - σ	Slope + σ
12.245	2.27E-06	1.37E-06	8.96E-07	3.64E-06
12.121	1.67E-06	1.51E-06	1.60E-07	3.18E-06
12.000	1.76E-07	1.64E-06	-1.47E-06	1.82E-06
10.286	-3.15E-07	1.96E-06	-2.27E-06	1.64E-06
9.000	-2.34E-06	2.23E-06	-4.58E-06	-1.11E-07

Table III. Selection of 0.9984°/cm model linear regression results.

Threshold Value (°/layer)	Slope	σ	Slope - σ	Slope + σ
18.000	6.13E-07	1.30E-06	-6.83E-07	1.91E-06
14.400	1.30E-06	1.57E-06	-2.68E-07	2.87E-06
12.000	3.67E-07	1.85E-06	-1.48E-06	2.22E-06
10.286	-6.69E-07	2.13E-06	-2.80E-06	1.47E-06
9.000	-4.36E-07	2.48E-06	-2.91E-06	2.04E-06

3.2. Results for Determining the Accuracy of the Discretization Method

After analyzing the trends in the data and the results of the linear regressions, the threshold was determined to be 12°/layer. Table II and Table III show samples of the results of the linear regressions for each of the models. 12°/layer is the first point where both cases have a slope with zero within one standard deviation.

Figure 4a and Figure 4b show all the data points from 0°/layer to 45°/layer for both models with logarithmic scales on the horizontal axes and linear scales on the vertical axes. The horizontal axes are inverted, with the higher values of °/layer on the left because as the amount of °/layer approaches zero the actual number of layers needed to construct the model approaches infinity.

This work does not intend to provide a definitive physical explanation for why 12°/layer is the threshold value for a rod of these dimensions, but a potential justifications is suggested. The point where two layers meet has an overhang because the layers are offset from each other by some angle. If the offset is a small enough angle, then the overhang will only expose a small amount of cladding. If the offset is large enough, however, then the overhang can also expose some of the fuel. Figure 5a shows how a small part of the fuel is exposed when there is 18°/layer of twist, and Figure 5b shows only cladding exposed when there is 12°/layer of twist.

It is likely that having fuel directly exposed to moderator will cause a slight increase in reactivity because there will be slightly less absorption of thermal neutrons before they reach the fuel. It is hypothesized that at about 12°/layer, all the fuel in the model has enough cladding between it and the moderator, that there is no longer any reactivity increase.

The results support the explanation that the overhang between layers causes an increase in reactivity. If the overhang at each layer is the cause of the increase in reactivity, then a model that has more axial layers should have a greater increase in reactivity. The 9.984°/cm model (results shown in Table II and Figure 4a) twists 10 times as much as the 0.9984°/cm model (results shown in Table III and Figure 4b). That means that when the two models have the same amount of twist/layer, there are 10 times as many axial layers in the 9.984°/cm model. This would cause the increase in reactivity before the inflection point to be significantly greater in the 9.984°/cm model. This effect is seen clearly in the graphs; the

(a) 9.9844°/cm model.

(b) 0.9984°/cm model.

Figure 4. Effect of twist/layer on the convergence of multiplication factor.

(a) 18°/layer.

(b) 12°/layer.

Figure 5. Overhang at layers.

Figure 6. Effect of the axial twist on the multiplication factor.

magnitude of the slope before the inflection point (from $12^\circ/\text{layer}$ to $45^\circ/\text{layer}$) is clearly much greater in the $9.984^\circ/\text{cm}$ model.

The suggested discretization threshold is only applicable to the model investigated here. If the threshold is related to the specific geometry of the rod, then rods with different parameters will have different threshold values than found in this work. The same process could be used to determine the threshold for a different fuel rod.

4. DETERMINING THE EFFECT OF AXIAL TWIST ON REACTIVITY

4.1. Methods for Determining the Effect of Axial Twist on Reactivity

After the threshold of $^\circ/\text{layer}$ for the approximation method was determined, the effect of twist on reactivity could be studied. This was done by varying the amount of twist/cm of fuel rods and observing the resulting changes in reactivity. While the twist in the fuel will affect other aspects of fuel performance such as thermal-hydraulics and actinide buildup, this work is focused on the reactivity effect of the twisted fuel.

For these tests, 90 models were created with twist ranging from $0^\circ/\text{cm}$ to $6.52^\circ/\text{cm}$; however, not all the points were evenly spaced. 41 of the 90 cases fall between $0^\circ/\text{cm}$ and $0.5^\circ/\text{cm}$ (total twist of 180°), and the remaining 49 cases are fairly evenly spaced between $0.5^\circ/\text{cm}$ and $6.52^\circ/\text{cm}$.

Each of these cases were run with two-million particles per cycle for a total of 50 inactive cycles and 100 active cycles, resulting in standard deviations between 4.5 pcm and 7.8 pcm. All the rods were made according to Table I and with enough layers that the amount of twist/layer was under the threshold from Section 3.2.

4.2. Results for Determining the Effect of Axial Twist on Reactivity

Looking at the results of the 90 cases in Figure 6, no line of best fit can be easily applied to the data. There are, however, a couple of significant observations. Every case that has some twist has higher reactivity than the case with no twist. The maximum increase in reactivity between any case and the case with no twist however, is only 40 pcm.

It is not clear why the reactivity increases more for some amounts of twist/cm than for others. The most significant result however, is that within the range of realistic amounts of twist, the reactivity effect of neglecting the twist is minimal. An error of less than 40 pcm would be the result of modeling a helical cruciform fuel rod with no twist, and in many cases, that amount of error is acceptable.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Helical cruciform fuel rods were constructed using Peacock in order to better understand how axial twist affects reactivity. The method used to create the geometry of these fuel rods was to separate the rod into discrete axial layers, offset from each other by equal amounts of twist. After testing, a maximum threshold of $12^\circ/\text{layer}$ was chosen as the point where the results (multiplication factors) effectively converge. Twist greater than $12^\circ/\text{layer}$ causes the multiplication factor of a model to increase as a result of approximation error. Adding more layers to decrease the twist to less than $12^\circ/\text{layer}$ would make the model appear smoother, but it should not significantly increase the accuracy of the model.

After the threshold was set, the effect of twist on reactivity was studied. Multiplication factors from cases ranging from $0^\circ/\text{cm}$ to $6.52^\circ/\text{cm}$ of twist were compared. No trend that relates twist to reactivity was identified in this work. The main conclusion was that the change in reactivity from a fuel rod with no twist to one with any realistic amount of twist is minimal. Twisting a rod any amount does cause the reactivity to increase, but in all cases tested, the reactivity increase was less than 40 pcm. These results provide assurance that the effect of the twist of helical cruciform fuel rods on the multiplication factor is indeed minimal. Given that the reactivity effect of twist is relatively small compared to other physical uncertainties, these results indicate that it may be reasonable to omit the twist and perform analysis of these fuel rods using two-dimensional lattice physics calculations.

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